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Concern about climate change in the Italian regions

It grew by 11.7% between 2012 and 2022 on average

Istat calculates the concern about climate change in the Italian regions. The variable is defined as the percentage of electricity consumption covered by renewable sources out of total gross internal consumption. The indicator is obtained as the ratio between the actual gross electricity production from RES (not normalised) and the Gross Domestic Consumption of electricity (equal to the gross production of electricity gross of production from pumping contributions plus the balance of exchanges with the abroad or between regions). The data refers to the Italian regions between 2012 and 2022.

Ranking of Italian regions by value of concern about climate change in Italian regions in 2022. In 2022, Italian regions showed varying degrees of concern about climate change, reflecting different environmental sensitivities and awareness. Below, I present an analysis of regions by values of concern about climate change. The Veneto region showed the highest level of concern about climate change in 2021, standing at 75.9%. Tuscany ranks second with a significant percentage of 73.4%, confirming a notable environmental commitment. The Marche follows closely with a concern rate of 72.8%, highlighting significant environmental sensitivity among residents. Lazio ranks fourth with a concern percentage of 72.4%, maintaining a sustained interest in climate issues. Piedmont occupies fifth position, with 71.9% of the population expressing concern about climate change. It should be noted that Calabria reported the lowest level of concern with 62%, representing an exception among Italian regions. The variety of positions reflects the heterogeneity of approaches and priorities in the context of environmental awareness.

Change in concern about climate change in Italian regions between 2012 and 2022. Over the decade between 2012 and 2022, Italian regions showed significant changes in concern about climate change. Concern about climate change generally increased in all regions analyzed during this period. Regions such as Umbria (+19.2%), Piedmont (+17.9%), Tuscany (+16.7%), and Lombardy (+16.4%) have seen substantial increases in concern, indicating growing interest and environmental awareness. Other regions such as Valle d'Aosta, Liguria, Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Emilia-Romagna and Marche showed positive variations, but to a slightly more moderate extent than the previous ones. In contrast, Calabria showed a negative change of -9.1%, representing the only region with a decrease in concern about climate change. These data underline the growing importance that the environmental issue is assuming in the perceptions of the Italian population, with an ever-increasing commitment to recognizing and addressing the challenges linked to climate change.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. The clustering analysis with k-Means algorithm shows the presence of three clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Piedmont, Liguria, Lombardy, Lazio, Molise, Sicily;
- Cluster 2: Valle d'Aosta, Campania, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria, Sardinia;

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- Cluster 3: Trentino Alto Adige, Emilia Romagna, Tuscany, Marche, Abruzzo.

We can see that the southern regions tend to have a lower value of concern for the environmental condition. The only regions that have high levels of concern about environmental conditions are Molise and Abruzzo.

Concern about climate change-CCC in Italian macro-regions. At the national level, concern about climate change appears to have increased in 2016, followed by a more or less constant level in subsequent years. Overall, Italy shows sustained concern about this issue. There are variations in the percentages of concern between different regions and macro-regions. For example, the Northern regions appear to show higher levels of concern than the South and the Islands. In 2019, a peak of concern was noted in many regions, followed by a general maintenance of high levels in the following two years (2020-2021). In 2019, the North-East appears to be the region most concerned about climate change, followed by the North and Central. The Northern regions appear to show a more stable trend over time, while the South and the Islands may have more significant fluctuations.

Estimating the value of concern about climate change. In particular, we estimated the following equation:

$$CCC_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(SC)_{it} + \beta_2(IMC)_{it} + \beta_3(CBL)_{it} + \beta_4(SSAC)_{it}$$

Where $i=20$ and $t=[2012;2022]$.

Concern about climate change is positively connected with the following variables:

- **Swimmable Coasts-SC:** The interconnection between growing concern about climate change and the preservation of swimmable coasts is evident through several mechanisms. The increase in awareness and anxiety regarding environmental impacts, particularly related to climate change, is positively reflected in practices and decisions related to coastal areas designated for beach activities. Those who express strong concern about climate change usually demonstrate greater sensitivity to environmental impacts. This awareness drives the adoption of responsible behavior during seaside activities, promoting sustainable management of natural resources and helping to preserve the quality of marine waters. Active participation in conservation initiatives, such as cleaning beaches or protecting marine biodiversity, becomes a tangible way to translate environmental concern into concrete actions. Furthermore, those who feel involved in the environmental cause are more inclined to support sustainable coastal management policies, contributing to the creation of regulations and regulations to protect marine areas. Sustainability becomes a guiding principle in the beach practices of those concerned about climate change. This translates into responsible behavior, such as correct waste management, reduction of environmental impact and support for tourist facilities that adopt environmentally friendly practices. Ultimately, the growing concern about climate change creates a positive synergy with the conservation of bathing marine coasts. This report promotes a more conscious, responsible and sustainable approach to human activities along the coasts, thus contributing to the preservation of these ecosystems crucial for environmental well-being and the enjoyment of future generations.
- **Internal material consumption-IMC:** in particular situations and local contexts, a positive relationship emerges between concern for climate change and internal material consumption in Italian regions. This could be due to the development of eco-sustainable sectors, circular production initiatives, environmental education focused on local production, sustainable

development projects and support for local businesses that adopt sustainable practices. However, globally, the trend remains for decreased material consumption in response to growing environmental awareness.

- Concern about biodiversity loss-CBL: The growing concern about climate change is closely related to the growing attention to biodiversity loss in a broader environmental discourse. This connection is based on several key elements that emerge in debates and conversations about environmental challenges. First, the shared awareness of the anthropogenic origin of both problems provides a solid basis for the connection between climate change and biodiversity loss. Human activities, such as sustainable use of resources and reduction of emissions, are often cited as common solutions to both issues. Understanding the similarity in impacts on ecosystems is a crucial point of discussion. Climate variability affects the distribution of species, while habitat loss and land fragmentation directly contribute to the decrease in biological diversity. This common recognition suggests the need to address issues in an integrated way. Environmental discourse also recognizes that responses to the challenges of climate change often overlap with actions needed to preserve biodiversity. Concepts such as the protection of natural habitats, the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices and the transition to renewable energy sources emerge as shared strategies. Furthermore, awareness of the interdependence of ecosystems emerges in the discourses, underlining that the loss of biodiversity can weaken the resilience of ecosystems and make them more susceptible to the impacts of climate change and vice versa. Finally, in a broader context, those who worry about changes climate change researchers tend to take a broader perspective on environmental challenges. This more comprehensive view leads to greater concern about biodiversity loss, viewing it as an integral part of complex global environmental challenges. In summary, the positive relationship between concern about climate change and concern about biodiversity loss emerges discursively through shared understanding of anthropogenic causes, similar impacts on ecosystems, and integrated responses needed to preserve the environment.

There is a negative relationship between concern about climate change and:

- Soil sealing from artificial cover-SSAC: Growing concern about climate change is closely linked to a reduction in soil sealing from artificial cover, suggesting a growing awareness of environmental impacts and the promotion of more sustainable practices in urban planning decisions. Those who are sensitive to these issues tend to adopt a more sustainable approach to urban planning. This could manifest itself through support for policies that limit the expansion of impervious areas, favoring solutions that favor soil permeability and the conservation of urban green spaces. Furthermore, awareness of water-related impacts, such as flooding and water quality degradation, drives urban planning decisions aimed at minimizing soil sealing. Active participation in environmental movements and the integration of sustainability principles into urban planning decisions represent tangible manifestations of this negative relationship. Ultimately, the growing concern about climate change can be seen as a catalyst for more sustainable urban planning actions and decisions, aimed at reducing soil sealing and promoting more environmentally sensitive urban development.

Conclusions. Concern about climate change grew by 11.7% between 2012 and 2021 in Italian regions. This value has also grown in the Italian macro-regions. However, a significant difference persists between northern regions which have medium-high levels of concern about climate change and southern regions which have medium-low levels. Promoting environmental concern and awareness in Italian regions is a crucial challenge that requires a careful and motivating discursive approach. To

address this issue, it is essential to build a discourse that stimulates individual and collective commitment towards more sustainable behaviors and also:

- Promote environmental education as a key tool for raising awareness.
- Highlight the importance of educational programs in schools, workplaces and communities.
- Illustrate the tangible benefits resulting from sustainable behaviors. This can include improved air quality, greater biodiversity, energy savings and improvements in public health.
- Promote a local sustainability approach.
- Highlight sustainable initiatives already underway in Italian regions and how they can be replicated or expanded.
- Encourage the active participation of local communities.
- Discuss the creation of volunteer groups, online forums and other platforms that allow citizens to contribute to environmental decisions.
- Highlight the importance of collaboration between public and private sectors, institutions, non-governmental organizations and citizens.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	61	58,1	58,8	61,9	66,9	60,9	66,4	71,3	70,3	66,2	71,9
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	62,5	58,5	53,1	62,4	59,9	59,1	65,9	74	66,9	64,9	71,4
Liguria	62,6	59,8	58,2	63,8	63,8	64	65,3	68,8	71,1	65,3	71
Lombardia	61,6	54,9	57,2	61,3	66,5	63,9	68,4	69,5	72	67,9	71,7
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	62,1	61,9	59,1	62,7	66,8	66,4	66	71,3	69,8	66,9	69,6
Veneto	67,9	64,7	61,3	62,6	68,7	66,2	67,2	72,1	71,8	68,6	75,9
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	65,4	60,6	60,5	64,1	66,7	64,7	70	72,6	69,4	67,3	71,5
Emilia-Romagna	62,1	58	59,5	64,6	69,4	66,3	67,9	76,1	75,2	68,2	69,8
Toscana	62,9	62,4	57,7	62,4	67	65	68,2	72,4	70,8	70,1	73,4
Umbria	59,8	55,6	61,6	62,2	64,2	64,1	69,6	77,5	65,9	66,5	71,3

Marche	61,9	60,8	58	62,1	71,9	66,4	64,7	72,4	69,7	69,3	72,8
Lazio	64,3	59,3	57,3	60,1	63,1	63,9	66,7	71,1	70,9	67,2	72,4
Abruzzo	60,2	62,2	59,1	62,9	67,6	69,6	71,5	70,8	70,8	67,5	71,8
Molise	64,1	53,2	59,4	67,1	65	60,7	64,8	65,9	77,1	70,3	68,9
Campania	61,5	59,7	56,6	57,6	60,2	62,7	62,3	68,5	65,8	61,6	68,7
Puglia	65,5	62	62,2	61,1	66	59,8	66,4	68,5	64,5	66,8	66,4
Basilicata	62,8	59,4	57	53,2	60,7	58,7	68,3	66,6	70,8	64,3	67,9
Calabria	68,2	56,4	57,2	63,5	68,7	63,1	64,4	67,1	61,9	60,4	62
Sicilia	65,1	57,7	60,7	64,6	63,7	62,6	65,5	73,1	70,8	63,3	71,3
Sardegna	61,8	58,4	55,8	57,7	67,1	61,6	61,7	71,8	69,7	66,3	71

A94	Concern about climate change
A87	Bathing sea coasts
A89	Soil waterproofing from artificial cover
A90	Internal material consumption
A96	Concern about biodiversity loss

Rank	Regione	2012	2022	Variazione assoluta	Variazione Percentuale
1	Abruzzo	60,2	71,8	11,6	19,3
2	Umbria	59,8	71,3	11,5	19,2
3	Piemonte	61	71,9	10,9	17,9
4	Marche	61,9	72,8	10,9	17,6
5	Toscana	62,9	73,4	10,5	16,7
6	Lombardia	61,6	71,7	10,1	16,4
7	Sardegna	61,8	71	9,2	14,9
8	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	62,5	71,4	8,9	14,2
9	Liguria	62,6	71	8,4	13,4
10	Lazio	64,3	72,4	8,1	12,6
11	Emilia-Romagna	62,1	69,8	7,7	12,4
12	Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	62,1	69,6	7,5	12,1
13	Veneto	67,9	75,9	8	11,8
14	Campania	61,5	68,7	7,2	11,7
15	Sicilia	65,1	71,3	6,2	9,5
16	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	65,4	71,5	6,1	9,3
17	Basilicata	62,8	67,9	5,1	8,1
18	Molise	64,1	68,9	4,8	7,5
19	Puglia	65,5	66,4	0,9	1,4
20	Calabria	68,2	62	-6,2	-9,1

